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ISSUES RELATING TO FUNDING OF POLITICAL PARTIES AND THEIR REFORMS

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ABSTRACT

Political parties and election campaigns are allied to the democracy and for that they require abundant resources. Just few years back, state funding for elections was suggested in the past in response to the high cost of elections and as a measure against corruption in the electoral process but there are MNCs, big corporations and industries funding without keeping any account or records which actually raises the issues of black marketing and corruption. Therefore this article will focus on issues relating to funding, laws and legal reforms dealing with elections and political parties.

Keywords: VVPATs, EVM, MNCs, EC, ECI, RPA Election, Political Parties, Democracy, Reforms.

Introduction: Political party funding refers to finance or resources associated with election campaign of candidate and also the expenditure of the political parties which includes political activity during the non-election period like integration and mobilization of citizens, for the formulation of policies related to public, recruitment of the political leaders and for the organization of parliament and government.* The resources for these purposes are either raised by the parties, the candidates on their own or provided by way of state funding. The state funding is provided either directly or in indirect manner. Direct state funding is given to political parties and or candidates in form of money, usually as bank transfer. Indirect state funding refers to transfer of resources by the state or the government to a political party or a candidate for a monetary value in indirect way.

Recently, there was a debate on electoral reforms in the Rajya Sabha on 22/03/2017. Even the members of political parties were avoiding discussions on electoral reforms,

except in private conversations. But the participation in the debate on that day was so enthusiastic that the deputy chairman had to extend the discussion to twice the time that is normally allotted to a short duration discussion two-and-a half hours to five hours. The provocation for the debate was BSP's allegation of manipulation of EVMs in the recent UP assembly elections. As expected, issues about EVMs took up a major part of the discussion. Also the system of ballot papers was mentioned; most speakers demanded the use of VVPATs (voter-verified paper audit trail) in the forthcoming elections to the Gujarat and Himachal Pradesh assemblies, and eventually in the Lok Sabha elections of 2019. In a judgement in 2013, *Subramanian Swamy v. ECI*¹ the Supreme Court had commended the Election Commission for taking a series of steps to introduce VVPATs, including conducting an all-party meeting in 2011. The meeting had unanimously approved the idea of introducing VVPATs. The EC had then ordered the two EVM companies to start manufacturing the machines and a field test were conducted in 2011 in five climatic zones. Our effort was to introduce these machines in the 2012 UP assembly

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elections and four other state assembly elections. That couldn't happen as the field tests revealed snags, which took almost a year to fix. Holding that the paper trail is an "indispensable requirement of free and fair elections", the Supreme Court directed the Government of India to provide the requisite funds for procuring the VVPAT machines. Appreciating the EC's efforts, the court approved its plan to roll out VVPATs in phases till 2019.²

Besides above, India has instances of donations and unaccounted money which government, court or committees are trying to curb. For example in 1960s the Congress and the Swatantra Party the latter started by C. Rajagopalachari as a party advocating free enterprises were the main beneficiaries of donations from big conglomerates such as the Tatas and the Birlas, who together accounted for 34 percent between 1962 and 1968. In 1969, a complete ban was imposed on corporate funding not only to break the nexus between politics and business but also to curb cronyism however this ban was revoked in 1985.³ The step was taken by the Supreme Court in 1974 in one of the famous case *Kanwar Lal Gupta v. Amar Nath Chawla*,⁴ where it was held that party expenditures in support of a candidate would count toward the candidate expenditure ceiling.

"...money is bound to play an important part in the successful prosecution of an election campaign. Money supplies "assets for advertising and other forms of political solicitation that increases the candidate's exposure to the public." Not only can money buy advertising and canvassing facilities such as hoardings, posters, handbills, brochures etc. and all the other paraphernalia of an election campaign, but it can also provide the means for quick and speedy communications and movements and sophisticated campaign techniques and is also "a substitute for energy" in that paid workers can be employed where volunteers are found to be insufficient. The availability of large funds does ordinarily tend to

increase the number of votes a candidate will receive. If, therefore, one political party or individual has larger resources available to it than another individual or political party, the former would certainly, under the present system of conducting elections, have an advantage over the latter in the electoral process". [Emphasis supplied]

This ruling party effectively bung a major loophole, which candidates had repeatedly exploited to circumvent strict expenditure limits. In 1975 the Congress government then amended the Representation of Peoples Act, 1951 in 1975, effectively overriding the Court's decision. In short order, parliament appended Explanation 1 to Section Sec. 77(1)

Sec. 77- Account of election expenses and maximum thereof-

- (1) *Every candidate at an election shall, either by himself or by his election agent, keep a separate and correct account of all expenditure in connection with the election incurred or authorised by him or by his election agent between 2[the date on which he has been nominated] and the date of declaration of the result thereof, both dates inclusive.*

Explanation 1.—for the removal of doubts, it is hereby declared that—

- (a) *the expenditure incurred by leaders of a political party on account of travel by air or by any other means of transport for propagating programme of the political party shall not be deemed to be the expenditure in connection with the election incurred or authorised by a candidate of that political party or his election agent for the purposes of this sub-section;*

In sort it stipulated that Party and independent supporter expenditures not authorized by the candidate would no longer count against the candidate spending limit. This amendment again expanded their expenses limits absurdly. The applicability of the same provision was again raised in Narayan Swami case,⁵ in the sense that

Explanation 1 of Sec 77(1) of RPA, encouraged corruption by underhand means. The court observed as under:-

“It is true that with the rise in the cost of mode of publicity for support of the candidate concerned, the individual candidates cannot fight the election without having the proper funds. At the same time it cannot be accepted such funds should come from hidden sources which are not available for public scrutiny. According to us, sub section (6) of sec 123 declaring incurring or authorising of expenditure in contravention of section 77 a corrupt practice has lost its significance and utility with the introduction of Explanation I of aforesaid which encourages corruption by underhand methods. If the call for purity of election is not to be reduced to a lip service or a slogan then the person investigating funds in furtherance of the prospects of the election of a candidate must be identified and located.”

After *C. Narayan Swani Case*, there is *Ashok Shankarrao Chavan Case*,⁶ where candidates and Political Parties have their ingenious means to generate the funds.

The Supreme Court observed:

“It is common knowledge as is widely published in the Press and Media that nowadays in public elections payment of cash to the electorate is rampant and the Election Commission finds it extremely difficult to control such a menace. There is no truthfulness in the attitude and actions of the contesting candidates in sticking to the requirement of law, in particular to Section 77 and there is every attempt being made to violate the restrictions imposed in the matter of incurring election expenses with a view to woo the electorate concerned and thereby, gaining their votes in their favour by corrupt means viz by purchasing the votes...”

It is unfortunate that those who are really interested in the welfare of society and who are incapable of indulging in any such corrupt practices are virtually sidelined and are treated as totally ineligible for contesting the elections.” [Emphasis supplied]

With the help of these cases, it is manifestly clear that Judiciary has been continuously wooing against the illegal funding of political parties to evade the corruption. Further apart from Sec. 77, Sec. 78 on expenditure of political parties and Sec. 29 B on Limits on Contribution as dealt under RPA, 1951, there are some other laws like Election Rules, Companies Act, the IT Act, and the Foreign Contribution (Regulation) Act where the description regarding limit of expenditure and penalties are also given along with the penalty. For example **Rule 90, Election Rules, 1961** as amended by Conduct of Elections (Amendment) Rules, 2014⁷ increased the ceiling for Lok Sabha poll to Rs. 70 lakh per candidate from the existing Rs. 40 lakh, and for the Assembly poll to Rs. 28 lakh from 16 lakh. Apart from that in Arunachal Pradesh, Goa, Sikkim, Andaman and Nikobar Islands, Chandigarh, Dadra and Nagar Haveli, Daman and Diu, Lakshdweep and Puducherry, the ceiling poll for Lok Sabha is 54 lakh. For Assembly elections, the new ceiling in Arunachal Pradesh, Goa, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tripura, and Puducherry is 20 lakh.⁸

Laws dealing with the Limits and Disclosure of contribution and donation

Section 182(1) of Companies Act, 2013 and S. 3 and 4, Foreign Contribution (Regulation) Act, 2010 talk about Limits on Contribution as Corporate contributions to political parties are allowed as long as the (non-government) company is three years old; its aggregate contribution in every financial year is below 7.5% of its average net profits during the three immediately preceding financial years; and it is authorized by a Board of Directors' resolution. Secondly, Corporate contributions to parties or electoral trusts entitled to deduction from total income. Thirdly, Ban on foreign contribution to candidate or political party and lastly there is no limits on political party accepting contribution. Further the disclosure of contribution is dealt by Section 29C, RPA as the party by report details all contributions

above Rs. 20,000 received from any person or company submitted in each financial year to the Election Commission. Beyond this, Profit and Loss account will detail the total amount contributed and the name of the party to which contribution made in every financial year.⁹

Section 182(4) of the Companies Act, 2013 provides for penalties for corporate contributions in contravention with the provisions of Section 182 in the form of fines levied on the company up to five times the amount so contributed, or imprisonment up to six months along with a similar fine for any company officer who is in default.

As per Section 13 A of Income Tax Act, not only the exemption to political parties in respect of income from House property, other sources, capital gains and income by voluntary contribution received by political parties from any reason are provided but deductions will also be made applicable under Section 80GGB and 80GGC, if a contribution is made to the political party. On the other hand, it makes it clear that if the candidate is disqualified from being a voter or standing in elections if convicted of corrupt practices or there is any failure to lodge election expenses within 3 years then that political Party is not entitled to get any income tax exemptions.

Apart from the laws as give in Companies Act, and IT Act, there is section 75A which was added in RPA, 1951 in 2003 which requires that every elected candidate in a parliamentary constituency to furnish information relating to their assets and liabilities to the Lok Sabha Speaker or the Rajya Sabha Chairperson within 90 of taking the oath for their seat in Parliament.

After discussing about the pertinent laws on contribution and expenses of political parties, there are some Committees and Commission which also have analysed the issues relating to electoral reforms in their reports. Since 1972 these issues are being debated when Joint Committee of Parliament on Amendments to Election Law expressed their views that electoral reform is

only possible when election expenses would be borne by a candidate or political party should be shifted to the state.¹⁰ Further it was continued by Sh. Jaya Prakash Narayan, a renowned political leader, set up a Tarkunde committee on financing of election and favoured the free public revenue as per the law. Apart from the above, there are various committees dealing with electoral reforms.

- The Goswami Committee on Electoral Reforms (1990)
- The Vohra Committee Report (1993)
- The Indrajit Gupta Committee on State Funding of Elections (1998)
- The Law Commission Report on Reform of the Electoral Laws (1999)
- The National Commission to Review the Working of the Constitution (2001)
- The ECI – Proposed Electoral Reforms (2004)
- The Second Administrative Reforms Commission (2008) (hereinafter (“ARC”))

These above mentioned committees first outlined the alarming discrepancy and irregularities of the Election process and then made recommendations for its implementation. The recommendations which were presented by these committees were not followed by legislature.

Conclusion: Undoubtedly, the Election Commission and judiciary have conducted a number of impressive electoral reforms to build up the democracy and improve the fairness of elections. These reforms are quite adequate and venerable but our system is still weighed down by many vices. To win votes, political parties resort to foul methods and corrupt practices and this corruption, unaccounted and unregulated donations are posing undue influence on politics and undermining the value of elections. In some countries, money from organized crime has gained control over elected officials and public institutions. These threats are posing a great risk to the

democracy of the country and losing the faith of people in politics and democratic process. Practically such maladies encourage the anti-social elements. The problem is not lack of laws, but lack of their strict implementation. In order to remove these unfair tendencies, there is a need to strengthen the hands of the EC and to give it more legal and institutional powers.

Suggestions:

1. There is a need to do away with expansion of parties. The EC should now register a party which has at least 100 registered electors as its members along with nominal fee.
2. The election commission should also control on the amount of money wasted in the campaigning of the political parties.
3. The Election Commission should be more vigilant when money power or muscle power is getting converted into vote power.

4. The Representation of People's Act should be amended as there are many provisions which are underpinning the political parties in their expenses and for non disclosure of contribution.

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